

Fig. 1: The ANS's first computer.

Fig. 2: Michael Bates at the terminal of the first computer.

This highly selective, rigorous, and competitive process means that only a comparatively few of the grant applications are ultimately successful. The fact that the ANS has been awarded several significant NEH grants in recent years speaks not only to the grant-writing abilities of the staff, but also to the value that academic and humanities professionals at large see in what it is we do.

Impact of NEH Funding at the ANS

The ANS has been based in Manhattan in New York City since its foundation, although its members can be found currently in 48 states (plus the District of Columbia) and 51 countries around the globe. Interest in numismatics is clearly universal, and through the decades we have addressed our members' interests primarily through events in New York City, occasional events elsewhere, and an extensive array of print publications. Given the logistics and expense of travel, few of our members from outside of the tri-state area are able to visit our headquarters and use our resources first hand. In order to make our resources widely available, we have embraced the potential offered by the World Wide Web to reach the largest possible audiences. The ANS's commitment to digitization, in fact, began decades ago.

Already in the late 1970s, when punch card main-frame computers the size of moving vans were the norm, and "personal computers" with a tiny fraction of the computing power of today's smart phones cost as much as a car, the ANS was making forays into digital technology. Under the direction of ANS President Harry W. Bass, Jr. (1978–1984), himself an amateur programmer and staunch proponent of all things computerized, the curatorial staff of the ANS, foremost William Metcalf and Michael Bates, began a program to create a new digital database of its collections with the assistance of George Cuhaj and several others, one of the first museums in the US to do so. As the World Wide Web began to expand beyond its initial limited networks in the 1990s, like many other institutions, the ANS saw an opportunity to present its computerized database to the world; Bass's Prime Information was the progenitor of today's MANTIS, a web-based catalogue of the ANS's numismatic holdings. The ANS launched its first website in 1997 (www.amnumsoc2.org), developed and financed by the Harry Bass Research Foundation. The site quickly became an important resource for those wanting to learn more about the Society and its collections, including those in the library. While the ANS continued to add new material to its online presence throughout the early 2000s, including early attempts at stand alone digital publications,

it was around the time that the ANS celebrated its 150th anniversary in 2008 that newly hired Andrew Meadows in conjunction with Sebastian Heath, who had already been serving as the Society's information technologist, began to explore uncharted digital numismatic territory. Their efforts, which resulted in the launch of Nomisma.org and the hiring of web guru, Ethan Gruber, now our Director of Data Science, helped solidify the ANS's reputation as a digital pioneer.

Today, over 30 years after the ANS obtained its first computer (figs. 1–2), much of the Society's efforts are directed towards creating new digital tools and resources for collectors, scholars, and the generally curious. Over the course of the last decade especially we have continued to improve our online presence with continual updates to our basic online resources, MANTIS (collections), DONUM (library), and ARCHER (archives), and have also pushed hard to create a new suite of innovative, interlinked research tools that focus more narrowly on certain parts of our large numismatic collection, such as Roman Imperial Coinage (OCRE). It is in part to fund the development of these new research tools that we have applied to the NEH.

At the same time, however, equally energetic work has gone into digitizing our entire print publication backlog, another endeavor the NEH has been funding. Our goal ultimately, is to have an extensive array of interlinked websites, any one of which can serve as a portal to the resources we make available. If, for example, a reader happens to be paging through the digital version of E. T. Newell's 1938 ANS publication, *Coinage of the Eastern Seleucid Mints*, and taps on the highlighted link to a coin in the ANS collection, s/he will be taken to the MANTIS record of the coin, which then provides additional links to Seleucid Coins Online, hoard information, maps, and biographical information on Seleucid rulers, and E. T. Newell himself.

In the meantime, we are getting ever closer to this goal largely due to funding from the NEH, which has already provided the means to hire several full time assistants to work on the cataloguing and photography work that lies behind our online tools. The NEH-funded tools that have already been launched, notably OCRE (numismatics.org/ocre), have had a significant impact well beyond New York City. In a Pocket Change blog post, ANS Executive Director, Ute Wartenberg used Google Analytics to illustrate the great extent to which OCRE is being used in the heartland of the US. Of all places, those in central

Minnesota appear to be some of the heaviest users of the site.

In sum, there is little question that without the support of the NEH the ANS would not be as effective as it is today in offering those interested in numismatics the means to explore the subject to the extent they can do so now.

BANNER ART BY ALAN ROCHE

Mission Accomplished: Online Coinage of the Roman Empire (OCRE)

Online Coins of the Roman Empire (OCRE)¹ is a major digital initiative begun in 2011 as a collaborative project between the American Numismatic Society and the Institute for the Study of the Ancient World (ISAW) at New York University. Its completion has been funded by a major \$300,000 grant provided by the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) in May 2013.

The original goal was to make available a digital corpus of all published Roman Imperial coin types, spanning the reigns of Augustus (30 BCE–14 CE) to Zeno (474–496 CE), according to the recorded Imperial coin types as defined in the 10-volume reference corpus *Roman Imperial Coinage*. At the same time, the project aimed at expanding toward external contributors with a potential for linking any collection-based online catalog.

The OCRE project is now complete, three years after the NEH grant was approved. The total number of recorded Imperial types reaches 42,740, a figure that incorporates a certain number of sub-types as well (fig. 1). Several key domestic and international institutions have joined the ANS in allowing users to access their own collections through the relevant types displayed by OCRE: to date, the British Museum, the Münzkabinett of the State Museum of Berlin, the Fitzwilliam Museum, the Harvard Art Museums, the Museu de Prehistòria de Valencia, the Münzkabinett of the Kunst Historisches Museum in Vienna, and the University of Virginia Art Museum are among the main contributors, having provided thousands of their coins alongside those in the ANS collection. As a result, the number of individual coin types records available through OCRE now totals more than 106,000. That number continues to grow as new institutions join the OCRE initiative or existing partners make more of their coins available.

Many of these records are accompanied by photo-

graphs, a tremendous accomplishment since it has involved photographing substantial portions of the collections, including about 30,000 additional Roman coins at the ANS alone over the course of three years.

OCRE serves as both a searchable catalog and a tool with which to conduct quantitative and typological analyses of numismatic data, encouraging collectors and scholars alike to approach Roman coinage from a variety of perspectives. Data in OCRE can be extracted through various search methods to produce innovative results. Users can narrow their samples by selecting specific target characteristics, including but not limited to mints, denominations, authorities, date ranges, monuments, and deities. From a data analysis perspective, it is already possible to work out the chronological distribution of images, monuments, deities, or concepts throughout over 130 relevant minting authorities, mints, or denominations. However, new analytics will allow even easier and more powerful tools for conducting numerical and quantitative analysis.

We will soon be unveiling instructional videos on the OCRE website to assist browsers in using these features. Whenever they are available, each coin type is appended with multiple examples from important numismatic collections, comprised of both metrological information and photographs of the obverse and reverse of each coin when pictured, as well as specific characteristics and provenance when known (figs. 2–3). OCRE is built on Numishare, an open source suite of applications for managing and publishing numismatic collections on the web. The underlying data model of the collection is the Numismatic Description Standard (NUDS), a linked and data-influenced XML schema for coins. NUDS enables the linking of coin types in OCRE to numismatic concepts represented on Nomisma.org as well as linking to web resources that describe physical specimens, such as those in the ANS. The use of linked data to link each example to the object record of its collaborative institution allows these images to make the types more accessible. This will allow users

1. numismatics.org/ocre.

Fig. 1: 42,740 coin types.

Fig. 2: Nero RIC 170 coin type.

Fig. 3: Available coins from several contributing collections for Nero RIC 170.

to conduct die studies when the available samples grow as more collections join the project. The use of linked data also facilitates connections between OCRE and other digital collaborative projects at the ANS, such as Coinage of the Roman Republic Online (CRRO) and Coin Hoards of the Roman Republic (CHRR), as well as those of other institutions, as displayed on this map (fig. 4).

At the same time, translations in about 15 languages have been made available, with new languages currently being implemented, including Hungarian, Ukrainian, Danish and Turkish. Finnish and Hebrew will be added soon (fig. 5). By selecting a preferred language from one of the pull-down tabs, all of the text on the OCRE site automatically switches over to that language; this feature greatly expands the usability of the OCRE site to a considerably larger audience.

Web traffic has steadily increased over the lifetime of OCRE, with a number of monthly sessions in the 1,500–2,000 range at the end of 2013 to a current average of 7,000–8,000 (fig. 6). About half of the 12,000 users-to-date in 2017 are new, with an average of seven pages viewed per session in seven minutes. These statistics indicate that OCRE is hitting the mark in terms offering unprecedented research services to an every expanding body of users.

A new interface to aid in the identification of Roman imperial coins by non-specialists (archaeologists and collectors alike) has been made recently available. We hope that this will be especially useful for badly worn coins discovered in archaeological excavation. The interface, called “Identify a Coin”, allows users to identify coins based on visibly identifiable attributes (figs. 7–8). Selection of specific criteria leads the user into a subset of matches for further comparison (aided by the great number of images associated with coin types provided by Nomisma.org partner institutions). For example, a user of this interface can select the metal along with any recognizable characters on either the obverse or reverse legend, with wildcards (“*” characters) designating gaps in legibility. Users can also select from a nearly complete list of Imperial portraits as potential matches. The portraits are listed chronologically, first by dynasty, and then by personage within the dynasty (including empresses and children). In many cases, portrait images are available in gold, silver, and bronze, as well as worn examples that one may encounter with stray finds or excavation. The selection of a material will automatically change the metal of the portraits, when a relevant image is available. More than one material may be chosen, which is useful for later Roman coinage, when severe wear makes it difficult to distinguish between what RIC has designated as “silver,” “bronze,” or “billon.” By clicking the left

1st century	Messalina	Britannicus	Claudia Antonia	Claudia Octavia	Clodius Macer				
2nd century	Pompey (restored)	Sulla (restored)							
3rd century	Silbannacus	Sponsioanus	Aureolus	Zenobia	Domitian II	Saturninus	Bonusus	Amandus	
4th century	Flavia Iulia Constantia								
5th century	Ariadne	Leontius	Maximus of Barcelona	Sebastianus	Constantius III	Euphemia	Olybrius	Glycerius	Odoacer

Table 1.

Fig. 5: A multilingual platform.

Fig. 6: A regularly growing audience—monthly basis.

Fig. 7: Julio-Claudians, unworn coins.

Fig. 8: Same Julio-Claudians, worn coins.

and right arrows below the image, it is possible to scroll through available portraits, which may show several phases of portraiture, such as Nero, who grew from a teenager into adulthood over the course of his reign.

This interface is one of the most complete depictions of numismatic Roman Imperial portraiture, and the ANS hopes that it will also prove itself to be a useful art historical tool to trace the development of Roman portraiture from the Augustan period through the Soldier Emperors to the Tetrarchy until the end of the Roman Empire.

Interestingly, this new tool in OCRE has allowed the ANS to visualize in a more strikingly fashion where it lacks portrait coins among its collection of Roman Imperial Coins. The following table (table 1) summarizes those that are missing, which are mostly very rare coins because of the short reigns of the rulers or types that were produced in very limited numbers. It goes without saying that the ANS would be immensely grateful to any donors willing to fill in these gaps.

OCRE is by now a game-changer for anyone with an interest in Roman Imperial coinage. It has created a true community of users, as attested by the numerous correspondence and requests for changes we receive every day from all over the U.S. and Europe. In that respect, the ANS is grateful to the collectors and scholars alike who keep noticing and signaling mistakes and allow for a gradual and steady improvement of the dataset made available through OCRE and its contributing collections.

There are many who have contributed to OCRE. First and foremost we thank Spink, the publishers of RIC and the many scholars and authors who contributed to the RIC volumes. Roger Bagnall and Andrew Meadows, then Director and Deputy Director respectively of ISAW and the ANS, launched OCRE in 2011 and served as its directors. Ethan Gruber, Director of Data Science at the ANS, has been managing its digital aspects. Alan Roche, ANS Photographer, has been responsible for the integration of the new images, with the very significant contribution of Emma Pratte, an ANS intern who had graduated from Parson and shot thousands of ANS coins. On the curatorial side, Gilles Bransbourg’s own responsibility as Project Manager was greatly assisted by the invaluable contributions of a team of hard-working dedicated ANS assistants. These include Rachel Mullervy, Scott Weiss, Shannon Ness, Kristen Newby, Lauren Tomanelli, and most recently Disnarda Pinilla. At the same time, Dr. David Wigg-Wolf (of the German Archaeological Institute), acting as a consultant, offered his expertise in the field of late Roman coinage.

OCRE, alongside CRRO, CRRH, and PELLA, testifies to the major digital initiatives that have been undertaken by the ANS over the course of this last decade, and shows what can be achieved through the combination of private initiative, academic expertise, and public funding. We remain immensely grateful to the NEH for its continuing support of ANS projects and its immense impact on all humanities disciplines.

BANNER ART BY ALAN ROCHE

The Hellenistic Royal Coinage Project

With the success of the ANS's digital initiatives on Roman coinages, including those focused on Republican coinage (CRRO and CHRR) and Imperial coinage (OCRE), we began to turn our attention a few years ago to the Greek cabinet, devising new digital projects that would highlight the ANS's impressive collection of Hellenistic coinages particularly. In 2015, we launched PELLA¹ a site that has as its current focus the coinages in the name of Alexander the Great (fig. 1). The growth of PELLA to include now nearly 19,000 coins of 4,070 types has been greatly facilitated not just by a host of interns and volunteers at the ANS, but by our colleagues overseas in England, France, and Germany especially. Innovative new ways to use the data now available on PELLA were also the subject of a recent conference hosted at New College, University of Oxford.² With PELLA successfully underway, it was time to look to other Hellenistic coinages, and to search for funding to support our efforts.

In April, the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) announced that it had awarded the ANS a substantial grant of \$262,000 to fund the web-based

Hellenistic Royal Coinages (HRC) project. Under the direction of Curator Peter van Alfen and Data Scientist Ethan Gruber, this three-year project (Phase 1, planned for 2017–2020) promises to radically transform the ability of students, scholars, or collectors to identify and research Hellenistic royal coinages, and to incorporate this numismatic material into broad analyses of political, economic, and social history. The funds from this grant are being used to hire assistants to aid in the extensive photography, cataloguing, and typology work that lie at the heart of the project, which officially began on May 1.

The Background: Hellenistic Royal Coinages

Coinages are an entirely unique type of evidence for the ancient world. No other class of artifact embodies the same mixture of political, social, artistic and economic concerns. The product of politicized decision making, ancient coins entered the world through state payments, but then became instruments of economic exchange more broadly, sometimes with serious and far-reaching social consequences. The numbers that survive today tell us about the size of economies at a given moment and in particular places; their images and inscriptions

tell us about the self-perceptions of rulers or entire societies; their findspots help us map the extent of political powers and economic influence. Ancient coins are a great deal more than just dead currency.

Within a few centuries of their invention in the seventh century BCE, coins became preferred monetary instruments, but their use was mostly limited to the Greek world. This was to change dramatically following the conquest of the Persian Empire by Alexander the Great at the end of the fourth century BCE. A sudden and massive surge in coin production began using the ca. 4,700 tons of captured Persian gold and silver in areas of the Near East that had previously not seen coinage, first under Alexander himself and later under his successors.

The monetary consequences of this flood of new coinage and monetary metal were unparalleled, not just in the east, but in the Greek homelands as well, where many citystates stopped producing their own coins or began to produce imitations of Alexander's. After Alexander's death in 323 BCE, his successors, including Seleucus, Ptolemy, and Antigonos began to define their

individual kingdoms and soon initiated a new royal class of coinage that stood well apart from the traditional citystate issues (figs. 2–4). Taking cues from Alexander's coins, these royal coinages were distinctive in a number of ways, not least for the ruler portraits that appeared on coins for the first time in history. Today, these remarkable coins bear some of the most distinctive images to survive from the ancient world, and form a standard part of many museum collections.

In a period from which few contemporary historical accounts survive, royal Hellenistic coinages have the potential to provide critical insights into the rise and fall of powerful dynasties in the Mediterranean and Near East between ca. 323 and 30 BCE. They can inform us about large-scale conflicts, the movement of vast amounts of wealth across regions, as well as the transfer of wealth between social classes. But coinage can only be set to these tasks if it can be assembled in

1. numismatics.org/pella.

2. See <http://numismatics.org/pocketchange/oxford-pella/>.

Fig. 1: Macedonia. Silver tetradrachm of Alexander III the Great struck at Pella ca. 325–315 BC. Price 232 (ANS 1944.100.29383, E. T. Newell bequest) 26 mm.

Fig. 2: Susiana. Silver tetradrachm of Seleucus I struck at Susa ca. 301–295 BC. SC 173.14 (ANS 1944.100.74104, E. T. Newell bequest) 27 mm.

Fig. 3: Egypt. Gold tetradrachm of Ptolemy II struck at Alexandria, ca. 270–240 BC. Sv.604 (ANS 1944.100.75919, E. T. Newell bequest) 22 mm.

Fig. 4: Cyprus. Silver tetradrachm of Demetrius Poliorcetes struck at Salamis, ca. 306–300 BC. (ANS 1957.172.704, Hoyt Miller bequest) 26 mm.

Fig. 5: Thrace. Silver tetradrachm in the name of Alexander III the Great struck at Mesembria, ca. 125–65 BC. Price. 1094 (ANS 1944.100.35792, E. T. Newell bequest) 29 mm. The reverse of this coin includes inscriptions noting the stated authority (King Alexander), along with a symbol and two monograms.

large quantities. With the arrival of webbased tools for such assemblage, we are presented with the opportunity to bring together large amounts of evidence distributed across multiple collections, and thus to transform our understanding of an entire period of history.

Hellenistic Numismatic Evidence: Problems and Solutions

Hundreds of millions of royal coins were originally produced, hundreds of thousands exist today, and tens of thousands reside in single collections like that of the ANS, which alone holds 25,740 examples. Major collections are held in museums across the United States, as well as in the large national collections in London, Paris, Berlin, Vienna, and elsewhere. Like the ANS with its online catalogue MANTIS,³ most of these institutions provide webbased access to many of the royal coins in their collections. But despite this wealth of numismatic evidence available for research, the study of royal coinage is severely hampered by several problems:

1) Typologies and cataloguing. The coinages of Alexander the Great, the Seleucid kings of Syria, and the Ptolemaic kings of Egypt have been well studied and

typologies have been published in print, but those for Lysimachus of Thrace, the Antigonids of Macedonia, the Attalids of Pergamum, and the Bactrian kings of Central Asia still have not been. Of the existing typological studies, some now are long out of print while the more recent studies, in print or not, are prohibitively expensive thus restricting access for many researchers, whether students, scholars, or collectors. Equally problematic is the fact that even the more recent type catalogues have now been made obsolete by new finds and revised attributions. As a result, there has been little alignment of the cataloguing in different collections making it exceedingly difficult to compare types of coins or to identify new ones across collections or even within a single collection. This global lack of alignment is not only an impediment to research, but to collection curation and infield archaeological work as well, which often depends on comparative examples for determining attributions and dating of individual specimens. It is now quite obvious that printed books can no longer serve as the ideal medium for the publication of critical numismatic typologies, which need to be widely and openly accessible and easily updatable.

2) Monograms and symbols. Hellenistic royal coins are remarkably “chatty”; the reverses of the coins typically carry not just the name of the king, but also numerous additional monograms and symbols (fig. 5). These are not well understood. Some we know indicate the place (the “mint”) where the coin was produced; others may indicate additional administrative information, such as the subauthority (a “magistrate”) directly responsible for the coinage. These marks are often our sole clue for deducing where and when a coin was struck. To date there has been no attempt to collate the thousands of marks known from the individual series of royal coins into a universal, searchable repository. Such a tool would immediately allow connections to be made between, for example, different series of Seleucid coins, but also between Seleucid and other nonSeleucid coinages. This would further allow deductions about attributions and dating to be verified or corrected, and would give insight into the extent to which the marks were reused across time and space, which would help to resolve the purpose of some marks.

3) Access to provenance information, findspots information and archival resources. One of the most important and prolific scholars of royal coinage, Edward T. Newell (d. 1941) left to the ANS dozens of notebooks and unpublished manuscripts on royal coinages and hoards that remain highly relevant. Until recently access to these documents had been limited to visitors to the ANS. At the same time, files at the ANS containing notes, correspondence and photographs concerning hundreds of hoards of Hellenistic coins remain inaccessible to most researchers. These files form the basis for the terse descriptions of hoards found in the publications *Inventory of Greek Coin Hoards* (1973) and *Coin Hoards I–X* (1975–2010), detailing the findspots both for types of coins and for individual specimens. Open access to these archival resources would give researchers a better understanding of the circulation patterns of individual types of coins, and the provenance history of individual specimens.

Hellenistic Royal Coinage aims to provide a solution to all of these problems. Through the digitization of the ANS’s unrivalled collection of this material, in parallel with the conversion of existing print works to a Linked Open Data resource, it will offer a suite of open access online tools that will provide benchmark typologies for royal coinages beginning with those of Alexander the Great, the Seleucids, and the Ptolemies. In addition, it will provide a linkable and searchable repository of monograms and symbols, extensive information on findspots (hoards), and will provide full and interlinked access to critical archival resources held at the ANS.

Overview of HRC

HRC will be built around seven interlinked components, employing the principles of Linked Open Data, already successfully deployed in a number of other ANS projects (including the NEH funded OCRE project). These include three standalone online tools each of which is devoted to the coinage of a single royal dynasty. These are: (1) PELLA, with a focus on the Argeads of Macedonia including Alexander the Great; (2) Seleucid Coins Online (SCO); and (3) Ptolemaic Coins Online (PCO). Incorporated within these three tools will be (4) a monogram and symbols repository. Two additional standalone tools, (5) Greek Coin Hoards and (6) the scanned Newell notebooks, will provide full documentation of available hoard evidence and provenance information for many individual coins. While all of the standalone tools will be interlinked, they will also be united through a portal site, (7) Hellenistic Royal Coinages, that will serve as a union catalogue for global searches and as a platform for later expansion, which will focus on adding the coinages of the remaining Hellenistic dynasties (Phase 2, post-2020).

Portions of Phase 1 have, in fact, already been completed. Early versions of three out of the seven components of HRC have already been launched:

1) PELLA has as its initial focus the voluminous coinages of Alexander (III) the Great, his immediate successor Philip III Arrhidaeus, and those produced posthumously in their names. Later versions of PELLA will incorporate the earlier Argead kings from Alexander I to Philip II. The basic concept of PELLA, like that of SCO and PCO, is to establish stable URIs for each known variety of Alexander’s coinage and then to provide a highly functional tool for identifying individual types of coins within a larger dynastic series, to provide illustrations, information, and statistical analyses on as many examples of the individual types as possible, and to provide as much information as possible on hoards containing examples of the individual types. The typology of the current version of PELLA (v.1) is based on that of Martin Price’s *Coinage in the Name of Alexander the Great and Philip Arrhidaeus* (British Museum 1991).

A typical page on the PELLA website, that for Price type 4⁴ for example, provides (figs. 6-7): (1) a typological description (with links to the Nomisma.org thesaurus); (2) a map of hoard finds (with links to the relevant coin hoard page; see below); (3) links to and illustrations of 47 examples of Price type 4 found in the collections of the ANS and Münzkabinett in

3. <http://numismatics.org/search/>.

4. numismatics.org/pella/id/price.4.

Fig. 6: Screenshot of PELLA, Price 4, illustrating the typological section of the webpage (<http://numismatics.org/pella/id/price.4>).

Fig. 7: Screenshot of PELLA, Price 4, illustrating a portion of the examples section of the webpage (<http://numismatics.org/pella/id/price.4>).

Berlin; and (4) statistical analyses of the weights and die axes of these 47 coins. All told, the current version of PELLA catalogues 4,070 separate types of coinage with links to nearly 19,000 individual examples from twelve institutions located in the US, England, France and Germany;⁵ by the end of 2017, thousands of more additional examples will be added from collections in the U.S., France, and England. Continued development of PELLA has become a collaborative, international initiative, not just in order to add more examples of individual types, but to edit and revise as well. Since Price's 1991 typology is in need of extensive revision due to advances in scholarship over the last 25 years, a consortium of nearly a dozen researchers based in the U.S., England, Germany and France, is currently working to revise the typology, which will appear in PELLA v.2, planned for late 2017. PELLA will then serve as the model for SCO and PCO, both in terms of functionality and development. With initial

development work spearheaded by the ANS, others elsewhere will contribute to and facilitate further development of these tools.

2) In February 2015, the ANS launched a beta version of the Greek Coin Hoards website⁶ based on the 1973 ANS copublication *Inventory of Greek Coin Hoards (IGCH)*, which lists and provides basic descriptions of 2,387 hoards, the majority of which date from the Hellenistic period. The current version (v.1) feeds hoard findspot information to PELLA, and allows for rudimentary searches of hoard information (fig. 8). Further development of the tool is necessary, however, to achieve its full potential. This will include the incorporation of data from an additional ca. 2,400 hoards derived from the print publications *Coin Hoards* (vols. I–X), links to the catalogue records of coins found in individual hoards currently held in public collections, links to bibliography on the individual hoards, and, most importantly,

Fig. 8: Screenshot of IGCH 1664 (Demanhur hoard, 318 BC) as represented on coinhoards.org (<http://coinhoards.org/id/igch1664>).

Edward T. Newell hoard notebook, circa 1939

Newell, Edward Theodore, 1886-1941

Publication Statement

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Abstract

Notebook of handwritten notes on ancient Greek coin hoards, including Aleppo, 1893; Afun Kara Hissar, Arpagot, 1918; Adrianople; Asia Minor, 1929; Babylon, 1900; Byblus, 1901; Chalchic, 1905; Chalcidice (Olynthus?); Demanhur, 1900; Epistaurus, 1900; Gabal (Byblus), 1931; Homs, 1934; Homs, 1927; Khorsabad; Mesopotamia (Dunne); Nicomedia (probably Thessalian hoard); Tell Hatal, 1911; Thessalian, 1935. Also, one loose sheet of Pera Palace Hotel (Constantinople) letterhead containing four pages of notes labeled "Antioch" Hoard.

Index

Aleppo (Syria) Appears on: 1
Amphipolis Appears on: Loose 1
Asia Minor Appears on: Loose 1
Blanchard, Ralph Huntington, 1875-1936 Appears on: 17
Bronze Nummus, Alexandria, AD 295 - AD 296. 1944.100.122 Appears on: 12

Fig. 9: Screenshot of a Newell notebook recording observations of coins found in the Antioch Hoard (IGCH 1516) (<http://numismatics.org/archives/ark:/53695/nnan187715>).

the incorporation of the unpublished archival material held at the ANS on individual hoards. Development of coinhoards.org has been funded to date by the ANS and Stanford University.

3) The ANS maintains an online archives website, ARCHER.⁷ With a grant from the Gladys Kriebel Delmas Foundation, the ANS digitized more than 3,500 pages in 43 notebooks of Edward T. Newell for addition to ARCHER in 2015 (fig. 9). This was done in such a way as to allow interlinking between the digital notebooks, the ANS's online numismatic catalogue (MANTIS), and online library catalogue (DONUM). Thus, if a coin mentioned in the notebooks currently belongs to the ANS, readers are directed to that coin's record in MANTIS; if that coin had been published by Newell, readers are directed to the DONUM record for that publication; and if Newell discusses a hoard listed in IGCH, readers are directed to the relevant coinhoards.org page. To date,

roughly 15% of the groundwork for this crosslinking between the notebooks and other ANS catalogues has been completed. A great deal more work remains to complete this as well as to link the monograms and symbols noted by Newell to the planned repository for these marks.

The major work that remains for Phase 1 of HRC is then twofold: (1) adding functionality to existing tools; and (2) building new tools. Once completed, Phase 1 of HRC will have a transformative effect on our approach to this important body of material. In a matter of seconds, anyone with an internet connection will be able to gather a wealth of critical information on royal coinages for a variety of purposes, whether for academic research, museum cataloguing, or just general interest.

5. numismatics.org/pella/contributors.
6. <http://coinhoards.org/>.
7. <http://numismatics.org/archives/>.

BANNER ART BY ALAN ROCHE

Unlocking the Book: How \$106,000 Created Infinite Research Possibilities at the ANS

Arrested Content

It is 1996 in Columbia, Missouri, and I, Andrew Reinhard, am seated in the archaeology special collections room of Mizzou's Ellis Library reading about pottery for my MA thesis. One book is open, and I'm taking notes from it with a pen and notecards: related people, places, and events. I am also robbing the book for relevant bibliography. Taking a break, I walk downstairs to pay the library's Copy Center for the privilege of photocopying a few plates from the book. I walk over to the card catalogue to browse the physical card file for the new sources I found, only a couple of which are owned by the university. I walk over to the Interlibrary Loan desk to fill out request forms that with a little

luck will retrieve books for me in 2–4 weeks from other libraries around the country. I don't know (and cannot reach) many of the authors of the works I am citing. The pottery in the books are scattered internationally in museums and private collections I cannot afford to visit because of constraints in both time and money. When my thesis is defended successfully, two copies will be printed, one for the thesis library in the seminar room of the Department of Art History and Archaeology, and the other for the Ellis Library stacks where it sits, full of MA-level synthesis of material, which no one will be able to find and use unless they go looking for it specifically. Public Internet accessed via shared computers loaded with the Mosaic web browser would arrive a couple of weeks after my thesis defense. My thesis was a valuable personal exercise in learning how to research and write, but to the best of my knowledge, my

MA work remains undiscovered, unused, and uncited. Imprisoned.

The Printed Book-as-Gilded-Cage

Think of the last non-fiction book you read. Do you own it? Did you borrow it? What did you do with it after you read it? If you kept it, why? Printed non-fiction books do one thing really well: they preserve data and synthetic text and images as published at a single point in time. In fact, printed books work quite well as prisons for data. To access the information, I have to visit the physical copy of the book to find the data I am looking for. I can add notes in the margin that only I will ever see (like writing on a cell wall), or can take notes for something else that I am working on. The book goes back on the shelf. It will be unaware of what I do with the notes I just took. Any new information I find that

can update that book's scholarship will not appear in its pages (especially if it is out of print without hope of a reprint or new edition). The book is a one-way communication device. The author speaks to me through the pages, but I can't talk back (most notably if the author is dead). As far as scholarship goes, this is quite inefficient. So how do you improve on a book, as beautiful as that gilded cage might be (fig. 1)?

Prison Break

Books go out of print. They become rare. Depending on their content, their value might increase in direct proportion to their scarcity. While this is a boon to bibliophiles, collectors, and dealers, the rarity and expense of these books serve as two major barriers for most scholars. In the case of numismatic books, one must travel to a special collection or library in order to see

Fig. 1: Inside the ANS library.

Fig. 2: ANS library and Internet Archive assistant John Graffeo scans books and documents for both organizations.

Fig. 3: Full-screen scanned image and its actual-sized, printed counterpart.

these and use them in person (fig. 1). This requires time and money, and your access is limited by the library's opening hours, not to mention its location. As scholars and hobbyists, we tend to fetishize the book. We treat the book as an artifact (which it is), a mixture of physical form and intellectual content. For many researchers, however, the content is key, and should be accessible at any time, and hopefully at no charge. So how do we break the content out of its prison? Digitization.

This is easier said than done, but the results far outweigh the time and money required to convert the print to the digital, especially for out-of-print and rare books. So what are the benefits of a digital edition of a beloved text?

- **Preservation:** Thomas Jefferson favored the idea of producing multiple copies of printed documents in order to preserve and circulate ideas. This is especially important in the case for rare books where limited physical copies are often found in private or special collections with restricted access. Scanning and distributing these rare books preserves and promotes their content for those who need access to the written information (fig. 2) while reducing the need to handle the physical, delicate object. If the books become lost, destroyed, stolen, or hidden, their content remains public and accessible.
- **Accessibility:** As described above, digitizing books and putting them online makes their content available to anyone who wants it. That, however, is only one level of accessibility. Digital versions of printed material must be produced in such a way as to accommodate for offline as well as online use, and in a variety of formats. For some people, reading a book as a webpage is fine. Others might need a PDF to take with them into the field where there is either limited or no internet access. And some people would like to print the book from the digital source as print-on-demand (POD).

- **Connections:** The interdisciplinary nature of numismatics lends itself to the online, non-linear connections of the internet. Numismatic texts frequently include objects, people (past and present), places (past and present), events, other publications, and primary sources. Numismatics incorporates history, art history, archaeology, geography, economics, political science, and more, and nearly everything has a home online. With a digital edition of a numismatic text, the ANS can link directly from it to anywhere online while also making that text available to be linked to from the outside. What was once content locked in print is now publicly available for anyone to use, adding to a web of content and context. The digital book is a portal.

- **Images:** In most numismatic publications, images of coins are reproduced at 1:1 (actual size), occasionally accompanied by enlargements. With digital editions, these coin images can be enlarged on-screen possibly providing additional visual information about the coins depicted. Depending on the resolution of a book's scan, one can conceivably review coin images full-screen (fig. 3). One can also link images from the book to other images of similar material online (and vice versa).

Get Out of Jail Free

The American Numismatic Society has long championed the cause of making its data free to discover and use online. These Open Access initiatives include its online collections (MANTIS), archives (ARCHER), and library (DONUM), as well as international, collaborative efforts such as Nomisma.org (standardized vocabularies and authority lists), coinhoards.org (Inventory of Greek Coin Hoards), Online Coins of the Roman Empire (OCRE), and more.

Much of this Open Access work is funded through major federal grants. OCRE was funded by the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH), and the ANS's new major project on Hellenistic coinage received over \$250,000 in NEH funding earlier in 2017. As seen elsewhere in this issue of *ANS Magazine*, these federally funded projects openly provide numismatic data and images to all, fulfilling the Society's mission to "promote and advance the study, research, and appreciation of numismatics" (Article XVI, ANS By-Laws).

The pieces missing from the Open Access puzzle were the ANS's publications. In the 2000s, many of the ANS's older monographs and journal volumes were treated as "orphaned" and out-of-copyright by the Google Books Project, an effort to scan as many books as possible, placing them in the public domain. The non-fiction titles found a home in HathiTrust Digital Library (hathitrust.org) as semi-Open Access where only a percentage of pages could be read. In January 2015, the ANS signed an agreement with HathiTrust to make these scanned books available as completely Open Access under a Creative Commons license (fig. 4). The ANS, however, hoped to do more with its own titles. That opportunity presented itself almost immediately after the ANS signed the HathiTrust agreement. On January 15, 2015, the NEH's Office of Digital Humanities (ODH) jointly published with the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation a call for proposals for the new Humanities Open Book (HOB) Program:

The Humanities Open Book Program is designed to make outstanding out-of-print humanities books available to a

Fig. 4: ANS landing page on hathitrust.org.

Fig. 7: Side-by-side print and digital editions of *Coin Hoards (Numismatic Notes and Monographs 1)*, by Sydney P. Noe.

Fig. 8: Homepage of the ANS Digital Library.

Fig. 5: Example of and ANS EPUB 3 ebook.

Fig. 6: Sample of an ANS monograph encoded in TEI XML.

wide audience. By taking advantage of low-cost “ebook” technology, the program will allow teachers, students, scholars, and the public to read humanities books that have long been out of print. Traditionally, printed books have been the primary medium for expressing, communicating, and debating humanistic ideas. However, the vast majority of humanities books sell a small number of copies and then quickly go out of print. Most scholarly books printed since 1923 are not in the public domain and are not easily available to the general public. As a result, there is a huge, mostly untapped resource of remarkable scholarship going back decades that is largely unused by today’s scholars, teachers, students, and members of the public, many of whom turn first to the Internet when looking for information. Modern ebook technology can make these books far more accessible than they are today.

Funding from the NEH and Mellon Foundation would be used to create digital editions of out-of-print Humanities scholarship, bringing them into the public domain under a Creative Commons license and hosted by HathiTrust. The NEH-Mellon initiative required at the bare minimum deliverables in the form of EPUB 3, which has reflowable text and resizable fonts that can be fully searched on any e-reading device (fig. 5). Many academic publishers had yet to digitize their backlist, and others had yet to create a platform on which these digital editions could be shared. For the ANS, however, digital editions already existed, and a preliminary version of its Digital Library had already been built. So what could the ANS do with ebook funding that went above and beyond the minimum grant requirements in order to get its content out into the world?

With the Humanities Open Book Program, the ANS saw a chance to fund the next phase of its Open Access publications mission, namely being able to take its books that had already been scanned, encode them in TEI XML, and then provide the tagged content for anyone to use in any format (e.g., EPUB3, PDF, HTML, and print-on-demand). TEI is an acronym for “Text Encoding Initiative”, a standards-and-practices consortium for representing texts in digital form. TEI creates guidelines for people to follow when making machine-readable Humanities texts, or converted text that can appear in various digital formats. XML (extensible markup language) allows someone to take that TEI-encoded text before it appears online or in an ebook, and apply “tags” to various parts of it, which can then link to other content in the text, or online. For numismatic texts these XML tags could include links to related people, places, and events, as well as related items in the ANS’s online collections and elsewhere. By also tagging paragraphs, titles, headers, notes, images, and captions, the final digital text becomes universal, able to be read on computers, handheld devices, and even turned into a PDF or a print-on-demand book. No matter what the output, the underlying TEI-encoded text allows for linking to and from the content, adding value to already valuable books (fig. 6).

The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation liked the proposal and awarded the ANS \$45,000 in funding to follow through with the Humanities Open Book Program in 2016, completing TEI-encoding of 89 out-of-print, rare book-length publications. The ANS applied for and received an additional \$61,000 from the Mellon Foun-

dation in a second round of funding in March 2017 in order to make the ANS’s entire backlist of monographs available as Open Access. With the funding in-hand, it was time to create the digital editions as well as a home on the ANS’s website.

Building a Better Book

For the first round of the grant, under the project management of Andrew Reinhard, the ANS’s Director of Publications, and the technical guidance of Ethan Gruber, the ANS’s Director of Data Science, the ANS worked with a board of established numismatists to hand-pick its most popular, hard-to-find, and out-of-print titles to include. These came from a number of series beginning with Numismatic Notes and Monographs first published in 1920 (fig. 7). The books chosen also covered a wide swath of history, geographic regions, and coin-producing cultures. As all of these books had been scanned by Google and were in the public domain as PDFs, these files were sent to our TEI partner in India, AEL Data. The ANS had worked with AEL Data before when successfully creating the digital edition of Scott Miller’s *Medallic Art of the American Numismatic Society, 1865–2014*. Gruber had been introduced to AEL Data with a University of Virginia libraries project prior to being hired by the ANS.

At a cost of around \$300 per book, AEL Data extracted the text and images from each scanned PDF from Google, and then created a TEI XML file, which tagged all of the book’s elements as well as all proper nouns for people and places. The ANS received the files for the books on a rolling basis, and sent them to TEI specialist Whitney

Fig. 9: Linking Numismatic Studies 19 to the wider web of knowledge, including a gold stater of Alexander the Great minted in Lampsacus (328–323 BCE), ANS 1994.60.1.

Fig. 10: Logos for the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation and National Endowment for the Humanities.

TEI transformation into HTML for the web and EPUB, TEI into RDF, and TEI into Solr XML for full text indexing and faceted search. This framework was built on Orbeon, an XForms engine and web pipeline processor. Orbeon's Zip Processor was used to package the dynamically generated HTML content for the ebook, the ONIX metadata, and gathered all of the images into the Zip file for download. Additional XSLT development was undertaken to transform Pleiades annotations into the Open Annotation RDF model to facilitate participation in the Pelagios Project. In order to disseminate PDF and EPUB 3, existing Open Source XSLT stylesheets were adapted to transform TEI to XSL:FO (for PDF) and HTML required by the EPUB standard. These stylesheets are now open source and can be used/adapted by other projects that wish to publish ebooks.

The ANS has the HTML, EPUB 3, and PDF ebooks in its Digital Library. As per the conditions of the grant, the EPUB 3 files were also given to HathiTrust for archiving and dissemination. Based on the HathiTrust's hosting of these ebooks, they are now also accessible in Digital Public Library of America (DPLA), both organizations crawlable by internet search robots, making these materials available to users through major search engines. The ebooks are a gateway between disparate information systems, and through these documents we may bind our library, archive, and numismatic collections more closely together.

To provide some concrete evidence of the benefits of being part of the first round of the HOB Program, Gruber ran some diagnostics on the final four of the group of Mellon-funded American Numismatic Society-published ebooks, which were uploaded to the ANS's Digital Library. The statistics were derived through various SPARQL queries of the TEI->Open Annotation RDF:

- 349 mentions of 164 different Greek coin hoards published in Inventory of Greek Coin Hoards in 193 sections in 14 books.
- 266 unique references to Nomisma URIs. 146 are mints or regions, and 87 of these identifiers are matches with Pleiades places. These mint references

appear in 600 sections in 51 books. Including direct Pleiades references (and not only those which are implicit by means of Nomisma concordances), there are 621 sections in these 51 books, which will be accessible through the Pelagios Project.

- 97 of the 266 references are to people, most of whom are linked to Wikidata and VIAF entities that are, in turn, linked to other systems, such as Social Networks and Archival Context.
- More than 1,400 coins in the ANS collection are referenced.
- 139 Roman Imperial coin types in OCRE.
- 4 Roman Republican coin types in CRRO.

Thanks to the funding provided by the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, the framework and methodologies implemented in this project will be applied to further digitization here at the ANS as we move toward making our entire collection of monographs freely and openly accessible, and the ANS hopes that other academic publishers and learned societies will follow in our footsteps in this endeavor.

These books go beyond simple transcription and publication as EPUB files. With links to the ANS's own research databases internally and externally to Linked Open Data information systems, the ANS hopes that these works will be transformed into research portals to further context about the people, places, events, etc. mentioned in the text. Also, researchers interested about the entities, objects, coin hoards, etc., will have access to a wealth of historical information about these things and will gain access to the ANS's monographs not only from its own library, archive, and museum systems, but through projects such as Pelagios, DPLA, and other large-scale aggregators of cultural heritage materials (fig. 9).

What's Next?

With the successful completion of the first round of the HOB Program, the ANS begins Round 2, TEI-encoding its remaining monographs for free and open access. Gruber is writing a series of programming scripts that will automate and expedite the creation of tags in the

Christopher to complete the tagging. A Digital Humanities (DH) PhD student, Christopher is conversant in TEI XML and was able to tag and link numismatic and Humanities-specific names, places, and events to relevant authority records in external Linked Open Data vocabulary systems shared by the international DH community. ANS-related names were linked to the ANS's own archival authority records and made available through ARCHER. Other names from the Virtual International Authority File (VIAF, used by OCLC, the Online Computer Library Center) and Social Networks and Archival Context (SNAC) were inserted for modern people and corporations, with links made for relevant numismatic authorities published on nomisma.org. Ancient place names were linked to identifiers on the Pleiades Gazetteer of Ancient Places with geonames.org serving as the authority for modern place names. Christopher also forged additional links to coins in the ANS's or other database collections, and other numismatic online references such as OCRE and IGCH.

The original 89 books selected by the ANS for the first round of the Humanities Open Book Program had been made better and more useful for 21st-century scholars. The out-of-print titles were rescued from obscurity and were about to be made available for free. But there was one last loose end: where to make these digital editions available for download and use.

Creating a New Home for Old Books

In 2015 Gruber created the ANS's Digital Library (numismatics.org/digitalibrary/). Originally designed as a repository for unpublished numismatics MA and PhD theses and dissertations, the ANS decided to expand it to include digital editions of ANS publications (fig. 8). Upon receiving the Humanities Open Book Program grant in 2016, Gruber began building out that new functionality, making the final code available as open source. For those not technically minded, skip the next paragraph.

This extension of functionality included the authoring of three XSLT stylesheets to support TEI dissemination:

TEI XML files as received from AEL Data, making that code available as open source. These converted, digitized texts will join the first batch of books in the ANS's Digital Library and on hathitrust.org.

Looking ahead to the rest of 2017 and beyond, ANS Publications will begin converting PDFs of each new book into tagged TEI XML so that these robust, flexible digital editions are ready for Open Access distribution in the ANS's Digital Library one year following the print edition's publication. Reinhard's previous publishing experience and similar experimentation at the American School of Classical Studies at Athens (ASCSA) has shown that making digital editions available at no charge does not undercut sales of the print version. Many readers prefer to read printed books, but also appreciate the added functionality (and portability) of their digital counterparts. While the ANS continues to pursue modern distribution methods of published research, it will not stop its printed publication program. Print and digital will continue to work together, a harmonized union of text, data, and media, reaching all audiences.

Coda

It is 2017 in Columbia, Missouri. A graduate student sits in her carel at Mizzou's Department of Art History and Archaeology. She connects her laptop to the university's wifi and logs in to the University Libraries' website, running a search on the coinage of Alexander. She finds a record for *Alexander's Drachm Mints II: Lampsacus and Abydus*, by Margaret Thompson, published by the American Numismatic Society in 1991. The print edition is checked out (likely by her adviser), but the digital edition is available. She navigates to it, opens it with a click, and begins to read. People, places, events, and objects are highlighted throughout the text, and she clicks on each instance hunting for new data, a new direction for her research to take. She links to the

Pleiades entry for Lampsacus, which relates to Hellespontus and Troas, and also has a *Barrington Atlas* entry. She finds MANTIS links to coins minted under Alexander's authority at Lampsacus now in the ANS's permanent collection, but she also discovers many more coins at the ANS that were accessioned by the ANS after the book was published. Her data set has increased, giving her more specimens to work with and more leads to follow. She browses the collection in New York from her desk in Missouri, and ultimately decides that it is worth the trip to see these coins for herself. Having all of this access to digital content has both expanded and focused her research, giving her a plan of action, which includes seeing the originals in person.

While at the ANS, she visits the library to see a copy of the book that brought her here, an artifact from before the Internet. 8.5 x 11 inches, thin, with gold-stamped red cloth over cardboard covers. It feels and smells like a book. She flips through the pages and plates, the content familiar but a little alien in this format, and she wonders when was the last time someone had held this particular copy. Its pages are pristine. Unseen links lead from it to dozens of other books in the library, fanning out to hundreds of coins in the vault, then out doors and windows to places far beyond the ANS's building in the TriBeCa neighborhood. In her reverie, she returns the book to the wrong shelf, in effect losing it for the next guest who—while unable to find it in the stacks after a few minutes of frustrated looking—locates it online in seconds, ready to use, and linked to the wider world.

Acknowledgement

The ANS would like to thank Don Waters and his team at the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, and the National Endowment for the Humanities and its Office of Digital Humanities (fig. 11) for their continued, enthusiastic support of the ANS's Digital Humanities and Open Access projects.